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SMA/Py/ZnO as a new biocompatible polymer supported nanocatalyst for the synthesis of chromeno[2,3-d] pyrimidine-diones through a novel and efficient pathway

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ABSTRACT

An efficient and simple method for the synthesis of chromeno[2,3-d]pyrimidine-diones using SMA/Py/ZnO catalyst has been reported. Zinc oxide nanoparticles were coordinated on a modified poly(styrene-comaleic anhydride) (SMA) support to prevent agglomeration and reduction catalytic activity. The polymer support was easily prepared from the reaction of 3-aminopyridine with SMA. The catalyst was characterized by using various characterization techniques such as FTIR, ¹H NMR, SEM, and EDX. The catalytic activity of SMA/Py/ZnO for the synthesis of chromeno[2,3-d]pyrimidine-diones through a multicomponent reaction of 6-amino-1,3-dimethyl uracil, 3,4-methylenedioxyphenol, and an appropriate aryl aldehyde under solvent-free conditions was also studied.